

Microwave assisted preconcentration of trace elements with pyridoxine functionalized Amberlite XAD-4

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Abstract : Pyridoxine modified Amberlite XAD-4 has been synthesized by coupling it through an azo spacer. The resulting chelating resin, characterized by elemental analysis, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and infrared (IR) spectra, was used to preconcentrate Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn ions. Parameters, such as sorption capacity of the chelating resin, pH and eluent, were evaluated. The effects of electrolytes and cations on the preconcentration were also investigated. Furthermore, effect of microwave power was investigated on adsorption rate of these heavy metals. The obtained results show, time of extraction is reduced significantly by this modification. The procedure was validated by standard addition and comparison of obtained result by GFAAS method. The developed method was utilized for preconcentration and determination of Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn in wastewater and preconcentration of Pb in lipstick by inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry (ICP OES) with satisfactory results.

Keywords : Preconcentration, pyridoxine, Amberlite XAD-4, microwave assisted extraction, inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry (ICP OES).

Introduction

The use of instrumental methods for trace metal quantification frequently requires preconcentration procedures to lower the detection limits¹. These preconcentration methods include solvent extraction^{2,3}, coprecipitation⁴⁻⁷, flotation⁸⁻¹¹ and solid phase extraction¹²⁻¹⁴. Among all the preconcentration methods, chelating resin sorption method is one of the most effective multi element preconcentration methods because, it can provide more flexible working conditions together with good stability, selectivity, high concentrating ability, high capacity of metal ions and simple operation. Moreover, at the same time, demands for trace element determination and concentration using these modified resins are ever increasing. This is because such functional polymers can be employed for the preconcentration in trace metal analysis, particularly for water systems geological and biological samples¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

In this work, Amberlite XAD-4 was functionalized with pyridoxine and it has been investigated in detail for use in preconcentration procedures. The results show that

pyridoxine XAD-4 is a good chelating resin for preconcentration of Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn.

In conventional methods of solid phase extraction, a relatively long time is required to adsorb analyte to the resin. In a different way, a novel approach has been developed for the extraction of Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn by assisted of microwave power at atmospheric pressure and time and efficiency of extraction was comprised with conventional extraction method. By this modification, extraction time and efficiency significantly were improved.

Based on it, a new method for determining Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn by inductively coupled plasma-atomic emission spectrometry (ICP OES) after their preconcentration with Amberlite XAD-4-pyridoxine resin has been developed and applied to the analysis of wastewater and lipstick sample.

Experimental

Apparatus :

The Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were obtained using a 6700 Thermo Nicolet FTIR spectro-

meter. IR spectra were recorded in the range 400–4000 cm^{-1} by the KBr pellet method. The inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer ICP OES equipment (Integra XL, GBC, Australia) was used for the determination of metal ions.

Elemental analyses were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer elemental 100 analyzer (Rotkrewz, Switzerland). TGA analysis was carried out using a TGA-50H instrument (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan). A model 3510 Jenway pH-meter was used for pH measurements.

The microwave oven used for extraction provided by Samsung (South Korea) trademark operating at 2450 MHz. The maximum power of the oven was regulated at 1000 W. Two power levels, 30% (300 W) and 60% (600 W) were studied in order to examine the effect of microwave power. The dimensions of the interior cavity of the oven were $29 \times 37 \times 40$ cm.

Chemicals and reagents :

Unless otherwise stated, all reagents used were of analytical grade and all solutions were prepared with ultra pure water (Millipore). Standard lab ware and glass-ware were used cleaned with 10% solution of HNO_3 throughout and repeatedly and rinsed with ultra pure water, according to a published procedure¹⁹.

Stock solutions (1.0 g L^{-1}) of the elements were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of nitrate salts in 1.0% HNO_3 and further diluted daily prior to use.

XAD-4 resin (having a surface area in the range of $300\text{--}400 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and 40–60 mesh particle size) was procured from Aldrich (Milwaukee, USA). Before use, Amberlite XAD-4 was thoroughly washed according to the sequence of 4.0 mol L^{-1} HCl, distilled water, 1.0 mol L^{-1} NaOH and distilled water successively. Finally, it was washed with 10 mL of methanol and dried in air before further use.

Synthesis of pyridoxine-functionalized Amberlite XAD-4 resin :

Procedures described in the literature for similar reagents^{20,21} were used for the synthesis of pyridoxine-XAD. Amberlite XAD-4 beads (5 g) were treated with 10 mL of concentrated HNO_3 and 25 mL of concentrated H_2SO_4 , and the mixture was stirred at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h on an oil bath. The reaction mixture was then poured into 150 mL

of ice-cold water. Subsequently, it was filtered, washed repeatedly with distilled water until free from acid, and then treated with a mixture of 40 g of SnCl_2 , 45 mL of concentrated HCl, and 50 mL of ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 12 h at $90 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to reduce the nitrated form of the resin. The solid precipitate was then filtered off and washed with distilled water and 2 mol L^{-1} NaOH to get the free amino polymer.

The amino polymer was treated with 100 mL of 2 mol L^{-1} HCl for 30 min and washed with distilled water to remove the excess HCl. It was then suspended in 150 mL of ice-cold water and mixed with a diazotizing mixture of 1 mol L^{-1} HCl and 1 mol L^{-1} NaNO_2 in aliquots of 1 mL each time with constant stirring until the reaction mixture showed a permanent dark blue color with starch-iodide paper. The diazotized resin was then filtered, washed with ice-cold water, treated with pyridoxine solution (0.03 mol in 500 mL water), and stored for 40 h at $0\text{--}3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The resulting resin, which appeared as brown-colored beads, was finally washed and filtered. Schematic representation of the synthesis reaction sequence was shown in Fig. 1.

Recommended procedure for preconcentration and determination of metal ions :

Batch method :

The sample solution (100 mL) containing 0.1 mg of one of the six metal ions was taken in a glass container, after adjusting its pH to the optimum value. The 0.1-g of pyridoxine resin was added to the bottle and the mixture was and stirred for 30 min. The resin was filtered and sorbed metal ion was desorbed with 4 mol L^{-1} HNO_3 (25 mL). The concentration of metal ions was determined in the filtrate by ICP OES.

Batch microwave method :

The sample solution (100 mL) containing 0.1 mg of one of the six metal ions was taken in a glass container, after adjusting its pH to the optimum value (Fig. 1). The 0.1-g of pyridoxine resin was added to the bottle and the mixture was placed in microwave oven for 50 s in 300 watt. The resin was filtered and sorbed metal ion was desorbed with 4 mol L^{-1} HNO_3 (25 mL). The concentration of metal ions was determined in the filtrate by ICP OES.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of synthesis of XAD-4-pyridoxine.

Results and discussion

Characterization studies :

The TGA plot of the resin shows two-step mass loss up to 430°C . The 7.2% mass loss up to 120°C in the first step is due to sorbed water and suggests that approximately one water molecule per repeat unit of polymer is present. The mass loss in the second step was 44%.

The results of elemental analyses suggest that on average one pyridoxine molecule is present per two repeat unit of the polymeric support. The TGA plot was shown in Fig. 2.

IR spectrum of pyridoxine immobilized Amberlite XAD-4 exhibits two additional bands, one wide band at 3558 cm^{-1} and other at 1629 cm^{-1} which may be contributed by $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ group, respectively.

Effect of pH on quantitative enrichment :

The optimum pH of metal ions uptake was determined using the batch procedure. A suitable aliquot of the metal ion solution (Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn) was used at varying pHs. The percentages of sorbed metal were determined in supernatant liquid by ICP OES. The sorption

experiments were duplicated for all six metal ions. The optimum pH range is 5.5–6.6 for Cd; 4.0–7.0 for Cu, Co, Zn; 4.0–5.0 for Fe and for Pb 6.0–7.0 (Fig. 1).

Kinetics of metal sorption (classic method) :

To determine the rate of loading of Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn on the resin, batch experiments were carried out under the following conditions : 0.5 g resin beads were stirred with 100 mL of feed solution containing 0.1 mg each of Cd, Fe, Co, Zn and 0.2 mg of Pb at room temperature (25°C). At predetermined intervals, aliquots of 5.0 mL solution were taken out for analysis.

The concentration of metal ions in the supernatant solution was determined and the amount of metal ion loaded on the resin phase was calculated by mass balance (in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ resin). It was observed that an equilibrium time of about 30 min was required for 95–100% sorption.

Kinetics of metal sorption (microwave method) :

To investigate the effect of microwave on loading of Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn on the resin, batch experiments were carried out under the following conditions : 0.5 g resin beads were mixed with solution containing

Fig. 2. The TGA plot of the synthesis XAD-4-pyridoxine.

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on sorption of metal ions on XAD-4-pyridoxine.

0.1 mg each of Cd, Fe, Co, Zn and 0.2 mg each of Pb. Then, the mixture was placed in microwave oven for 10, 30, 50, 70, 90, 120, 150, 180 s in 300 watt.

Subsequently, the concentration of metal ions in the supernatant solution was determined and the amount of metal ion loaded on the resin phase was calculated by mass balance (in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ resin). It was observed that an

equilibrium time decrease significantly as, about 50 s was required for 95–100% sorption in this condition. Higher microwave powers are not suitable because of boiling of the solution.

Total sorption capacity :

The sorption capacity of the resin was determined by the batch process, by equilibrating 1.0 g of the resin sample with 100 mL of $50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ metal ion solution (Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn) for 24 h at their selected pH at 30 °C. The sorption capacity of the resin for each metal ion was calculated from the difference between the metal ion concentrations before and after desorption. The values are 198.4, 252.8, 311.9, 335.8, 389.2 and 312.7 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ for Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn, respectively.

Effect of temperature :

The temperature is an effective factor in the context of sorption on solid adsorbent and has two major effects on the sorption process. Increasing the temperature causes to change the equilibrium constant and sorption capacity of the adsorbent for a particular solute. In addition, changing temperature will increase the rate of diffusion of the solute molecules, or ions, across the external boundary

layer and in the internal pores of the adsorbent particles, owing to decrease in the viscosity of the solution and, also, increase in the solute mobility in the solution.

In the present study, the effect of temperature on the sorption was studied by adding a fixed amount of adsorbent (0.5 g) to a series of beakers filled with 100 mL diluted solutions containing different concentration of each metals. The beakers were then sealed and placed in a water bath shaker and shaken at 200 rpm with a required adsorbent time 1 h at 15, 25 and 55 °C at their selected pH. The amounts of selected metals at equilibrium Q (mg/g) on modified Amberlite XAD-4 was calculated from the following equation :

$$Q = \frac{(C_i - C_f)V}{W}$$

where C_i and C_f (mg/L) are the liquid phase concentrations of selected metals at initial and equilibrium, respectively, V (L) the volume of the solution and W (g) is the mass of adsorbent used.

The sorption capacity of pyridoxine resin was increased with increasing the temperature. The increase in the sorption capacity may be due to an increased equilibrium constant for sorption at higher temperature. In addition, the increase in the sorption capacity, Q_e , with the increase in the temperature, indicates that sorption is endothermic nature. For example, the relation between temperature and sorption capacity of Pb was shown in Fig. 2. Similar sorption capacity changes were observed by temperature with the other investigated metals.

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on sorption capacity of Pb on XAD-4-pyridoxine.

Selection of eluent :

The effect of different eluents (HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄ and EDTA) on desorption of these heavy metals were investigated with 10–25 mL of different eluents with several concentrations. The obtained results show that 2 mol L⁻¹ HCl is suitable for desorption of these metals. Thus desorption of heavy metals took place with 25 mL of 4 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃ solution.

Effect of matrix ions on preconcentration :

The effect of NaCl, KBr, KI, NaNO₃, Na₃PO₄, Na₂SO₄, humic acid, sodium citrate and cations such as Ca and Mg on the sorption of these six metal ions was studied. The results show in Table 1 that the tolerance limits of the investigated electrolytes or cations are very high. The reported tolerance limit is defined as the ion concentration causing a relative error < ±5%.

Application :

Determination of metal ions in wastewater :

The wastewaters were collected from the Ravand factory (Mashhad, Iran). The Ravand factory produces sodium hydroxide by an electrochemical method. The wastewater samples were acidified by HNO₃, filtered through 0.45-mm Millipore membrane filters, and mix with resin as mentioned in Batch microwave method section.

Along with wastewater sample, the samples were spiked with two amounts of Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn to examine the reliability of the method. The results are shown in Table 2.

Determination of lead in lipstick :

A weighed sample of 0.2 g lipstick was placed into a Teflon vessel and reacted with 8 mL concentrated nitric acid, left at room temperature for 4 h then placed in the oven overnight at 85 °C. After digestion, the sample was allowed to cool to room temperature. Furthermore, after adding 5 mL of 30% hydrogen peroxide, the sample solutions were heated at 85 °C for another hour. The clear supernatant was transferred to a polypropylene tube and it was diluted to 50 mL, with deionized water. Then lead content was separate and preconcentrate with microwave extraction by pyridoxine resin. Finally, concentration of lead was determined by ICP OES. Lead content was expressed as part per million wet weight (mg kg⁻¹

Table 1. Tolerance limits of electrolytes (n = 3)

Metal ions	Electrolytes or metal ions (mol L ⁻¹)								
	NaCl	KBr	KI	NaNO ₃	Na ₃ PO ₄	Na ₂ SO ₄	Sodium citrate	Ca	Mg
Cd	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.10	0.01	0.1	0.005	0.05	0.05
Pb	0.01	0.05	0.005	0.10	0.01	0.05	0.005	0.05	0.05
Fe	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.1	0.001	0.01	0.01
Co	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.10	0.01	0.1	0.001	0.01	0.01
Cu	0.1	0.05	0.005	0.10	0.01	0.1	0.001	0.01	0.01
Zn	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.10	0.01	0.1	0.001	0.01	0.01

Table 2. Determination of metal ions in wastewater

Ion	Added (mg L ⁻¹) ^a	Measured (mg L ⁻¹) ^a
Cd	0	2.12 ± 0.87
	5	6.54 ± 0.98
	10	11.64 ± 1.14
Pb	0	1.32 ± 0.54
	5	5.98 ± 0.97
	10	9.76 ± 1.15
Fe	0	39.53 ± 1.35
	5	43.31 ± 1.32
	10	48.12 ± 1.70
Co	0	0.12 ± 0.09
	5	5.21 ± 0.37
	10	9.86 ± 1.32
Cu	0	8.23 ± 1.15
	5	12.62 ± 1.67
	10	17.59 ± 1.19
Zn	0	78.21 ± 1.57
	5	82.43 ± 1.34
	10	87.14 ± 1.87

^aThe results are reported as the average value from five sample measurements.

wet wt.). The validity of the proposed method was confirmed by comparing the results obtained from the sample analysis with those obtained by GFAAS (Table 3). Each analysis replicates three times.

Table 3. Lead contents (mg L⁻¹ wet wt.) in various lipstick samples

Brand	Color	Lead content (mg Kg ⁻¹)	Lead content (mg Kg ⁻¹)
		Proposed method	GFAAS
1	Shimmering pink	1.3 ± 0.8	1.2 ± 0.4
2	Orange	18.5 ± 0.7	18.1 ± 0.5
3	Brown	9.1 ± 1.4	8.6 ± 1.1

Conclusion

A chelating resin was prepared by coupling of pyridoxine to Amberlite XAD-4 in order to separate and preconcentrate of Cd, Pb, Fe, Co, Cu and Zn.

In this work for the first time, effect of microwave power at atmospheric pressure on extraction of these heavy metals was investigated. The extraction time for this method is significantly less than conventional approaches and extraction efficiency improve significantly.

The modified procedure has some benefits such as very faster rate of equilibrium, higher sorption rate. The obtained results show that the modified procedure has good potential for rapid trace enrichment of these heavy metals.

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